

CAPTURING THE OFF-AXIS BEHAVIOR OF THIN-PLY LAMINATES

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July 30th – August 4th 2023 - Belfast

Why thin-ply composites?

- High Versatility
- Tailored design
- Superior **strength to weight ratio**

The ACS3 spacecraft will showcase the ability to use composite deployable booms

Thin-ply composites made it to and flew on Mars in 2021

What's new...

The difference

Ply thickness $\geq 100 \mu\text{m}$

~~Matrix dominated~~
and
Fiber dominated

~~Interlaminar~~
and
Intralaminar

Decreasing ply thickness

Ply thickness $\leq 100 \mu\text{m}$

Amacher et al. (2014)

Options

An **Equivalent Single Layer (ESL)** approach seems fit.

The problem

A simple problem: Open Hole Tension

Elastic

Proper representation of the material at the ESL level:

- Macro-mechanical homogenization effects. ($[A]=[D]$, $[B]=0$)
- CLPT or other continuum approaches can represent the material with a homogenized compliance matrix $\varepsilon = S\sigma$ or $\sigma = C\varepsilon$

Fracture

How can directional toughness be defined ?

PF in a nutshell

It is a method relies on the **total potential energy minimization** linked to the variational expression of Griffith's energy balance.

$$\Pi(u) = U_e + U_f - W$$

$$U_f = \int_{\Gamma} G_c d\Gamma$$

$$U_e = g(\varphi) \int_V \frac{1}{2} \mathbf{C} \boldsymbol{\varepsilon}^2 dV$$

$$U_f = \int_{\Gamma} G_c d\Gamma \approx \int_V g_c \gamma(\varphi, \nabla \varphi) dV$$

The PF variable acts like a damage variable:

$\varphi = 0$ undamaged state

$\varphi = 1$ damaged state

crack surface density function

Governing equations:

$$\nabla \sigma = 0 \quad \text{in } V$$

$$\nabla \cdot \left(\frac{\partial U}{\partial \nabla \varphi} \right) - \frac{\partial U}{\partial \varphi} = 0 \quad \text{in } S$$

Evolution equation

Incorporating Fracture Energy Anisotropy

The crack surface density function:

$$\gamma(\varphi, \nabla\varphi) = \frac{1}{2l} \left(\varphi^2 - \frac{l}{2} \nabla\varphi \cdot \mathbf{A} \cdot \nabla\varphi \right)$$

length scale (pointing to l)
structural tensor (pointing to \mathbf{A})

$$\mathbf{A} = \mathbf{1} + a_1 \mathbf{a}_1 \otimes \mathbf{a}_1 + a_2 \mathbf{a}_2 \otimes \mathbf{a}_2$$

scaling constants (pointing to a_1 and a_2)

The new toughness:

$$G_C(\theta) = g_c \sqrt{\frac{l^*}{l}}$$

effective length scale (pointing to l^*)
Angle of crack with respect to the preferred \mathbf{a}_1 direction (pointing to θ)

$$l^* = l(1 + a_1 \sin^2(\theta) + a_2 \cos^2(\theta))$$

$$G_C(\theta) = g_c \sqrt{1 + a_1 \sin^2(\theta) + a_2 \cos^2(\theta)}$$

Inverse toughness, $G_C(\theta)^{-1}$, plot:

The “proper” scaling constants

If the path is **unknown or a predefined link to a direction exists**, then the toughness distribution will produce the crack angle as an output...

Inverse toughness:

$$G_c(\theta) = g_c \sqrt{1 + a_1 \sin^2(\theta) + a_2 \cos^2(\theta)}$$

Known Points P1, P2

$$a_1 = \left(\frac{G_c(90^\circ)}{g_c} \right)^2 - 1 \quad a_2 = \left(\frac{G_c(0^\circ)}{g_c} \right)^2 - 1$$

Application to off-axis tests

Experimental results from [Furtado et al. \(2021\)](#) for the off-axis OHT of a hard thin-ply laminate of lay-up: $[45/-45/0/45/-45/90/0/45/-45/90/0]_s$

	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	$G_c^{0^\circ}$ (N/mm)
Lamina	146.6	8.7	4.6	0.34	67
Laminate	54.0	48.3	4.6	0.39	19.7

Scaling constants: $a_1 = -0.9171$, $a_2 = -0.9399$

	Exp. Av.	FEA Prediction	Error (%)
On-axis (0°)	333.00	319.98	4.07
30°	334.00	318.62	4.83
60°	301.00	315.20	-4.51
90°	302.00	305.87	-1.27

Values of strength in MPa

Mitrou et al. (2023)

But...

The accurate predictability for the off-axis MD OHT seems to be linked to the **weak level** of anisotropy the plate has:

Assuming the SERR distribution is a valid indicator of a fracture toughness distribution

What is to be expected in **strongly anisotropic** plates?

e.g., the cross-ply...

There is a discrepancy in most angles

Testing for validation...

QI - $[90, -45, 0, 45]_{4s}$

H30 - $[90, 0, \pm 30, 0, 90, \pm 30]_{2s}$

H1575 - $[90, \pm 75, 0, \pm 15, 0, 90]_{2s}$

Weakest

Strongest

SOFT - $[90, \pm 45, 90, \pm 45, 90, 0]_{2s}$

H6015 - $[90, \pm 60, 0, \pm 15, 90, 0]_{2s}$

CP - $[90, 0]_{8s}$

■ $1/G_c(\theta)$

The soft one

Experimental results for the off-axis OHT of a “soft” thin-ply laminate of lay-up: $[90/\pm 45/90/\pm 45/90/0]_{2s}$ for T800-736LT from NTPT

Lamina	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	$G_c^{0^\circ}$ (N/mm)
	143.8	7.85	4.6	0.38	171

Scaling constants: $a_1 = -0.9657$, $a_2 = -0.8382$

	Exp. Av.	FEA Prediction	Error (%)
On-axis (0°)	635.89	634.51	-0.22
15°	655.56	645.45	-1.54
45°	738.75	698.745	-5.42
60°	797.51	741.7	-7.00

Values of strength in MPa

The H30

Experimental results for the off-axis OHT of a “hard” thin-ply laminate of lay-up: $[90/\pm 30/0/90/\pm 30]_{2s}$ for T800-736LT from NTPT

Lamina	E_x (GPa)	E_y (GPa)	G_{xy} (GPa)	ν_{xy}	$G_c^{0^\circ}$ (N/mm)
	143.8	7.85	4.6	0.38	171

Scaling constants: $a_1 = -0.8332$, $a_2 = -0.9330$

	Exp. Av.	FEA Prediction	Error (%)
On-axis (0°)	944.52	943.065	-0.15
15°	950.82	923.38	-2.89
45°	787.13	831.995	5.70
60°	721.61	805.18	11.58

Values of strength in MPa

The rest...

In fact, things get a bit more complicated...

H6015

The rest...

In fact, things get a bit more complicated...

H1575

Conclusions

- A PF ESL approach can be used to successfully predict **off-axis** notched strengths of MD thin-ply laminates residing in the weakly anisotropic range.
- There is a clear dependence of the overall behavior of MD thin-ply laminates to the level of anisotropy they exhibit

as for what follows...

- Continue exploring and developing methods and tools....

For listening up to here...

Thank you

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MSCA-ITN-H2020-861061

Directional Toughness

The toughness of a MD laminate can be determined by using as an input [Camanho and Catalanotti \(2011\)](#):

- Lay-up of the laminate
- Toughness of the 0° ply

$$G_c^L = \sum_{k=1}^n G_c^k v_k = \dots = G_c^0 E_{eq}^0 \sum_{k=1}^n \left(\Omega_k \frac{\chi_k}{\chi_0} \right)^2 \frac{v_k}{E_{eq}^k}$$

number of balanced sub-laminates

Scaling constants:

$$a_1 = \left(E_{eq}^0 \sum_{0^\circ} \left(\Omega_k \frac{\chi_k}{\chi_0} \right)^2 \frac{v_k}{E_{eq}^k} \right)^2 - 1$$

$$a_2 = \left(E_{eq}^0 \sum_{90^\circ} \left(\Omega_k \frac{\chi_k}{\chi_0} \right)^2 \frac{v_k}{E_{eq}^k} \right)^2 - 1$$

Essentially the Lay-up definition is changes to reflect a 90° rotation of the plies

VCCT technique for ERR distribution

